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Research Article

**GLOSSOPHOBIA : A COMPARATIVE STUDY AMONG
MEDICAL AND NON MEDICAL STUDENTS AT UNIVERSITY
OF LAHORE****Dr Noreena Aslam¹, Dr Shazia Hassan², Dr Mahwish Rasheed³**¹ University College of Medicine and Dentistry, Lahore, ² University Medical and Dental College, Faisalabad, ³ Punjab Medical College, Faisalabad.**Article Received:** April 2019**Accepted:** May 2019**Published:** June 2019**Abstract:**

Background: Glossophobia is speech anxiety due to the fear of public. It is a technical term given to a severe fear of public anxiety in the people who suffer from this anxiety get frozen in front of audience. They find their mouth dried up, their voice is weak and their body starts shivering. They may even go flushed and their heart starts thumping rapidly.

Aims And Objectives: The purpose of our study is to determine the prevalence of Glossophobia among medical and non medical students and to compare their prevalences. For this purpose a comparative study was conducted from June 5th to August 31st 2017 at University of Lahore, a convenient sample size of 150 students were selected the questionnaire was distributed among 75 medical students and 75 non medical students and SPSS was used to analyse it.

Results: According to our results the prevalence of Glossophobia was 53% among medical students while on the same grounds prevalence among non medical students was found to be 43%.

Conclusion: Thus, it was clear prevalence among medical students was higher than non medical students at University of Lahore. The social anxiety level was found higher among medical students than among non medical ones.

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INTRODUCTION:

Glossophobia is fear of public speaking. It is derived from two Greek words—Glossa, which means tongue, and Phobos, meaning fear (1). The person experiences dryness of mouth, a rise in blood pressure, reddening of the face, breathlessness, and the feeling of embarrassment and stupidity in front of others (2). Even in front of a small crowd, they tend to get confused. They experience severe anxiety before speaking—they start to tremble and their voice becomes feeble and dull. Sweating, blushing and palpitations is common as well. This affects about 75% of the world population. According to an analysis, its influence on people is more dreadful than that of the fear of death (3).

Symptoms of Glossophobia have three types: Physical, Verbal and Non verbal. The autonomic nervous system plays an important role in the occurrence of physical symptoms as it is concerned with the 'fight or flight' response of the body. Verbal symptoms are trembling and dullness of voice, pauses during a speech, which may help to relax the distressed speakers. Glossophobia affects both genders; however, females are likely to suffer more (4).

At a global level, anxiety is seen as a permanent threat. At a more local or situational level, anxiety can be experienced in response to a particular situation or act, for example, in giving a public speech(5). However, the question of how these constructs correspond to second language learning contexts is still under debate, although several interpretations of speech anxiety are offered in terms of the situational nature of anxiety (6).

At a local level, intense dread and nervousness are experienced if prompted to appear in front of the mass public and speak. Constant anxious thoughts and the nightmare of having a public embarrassment during speaking, weakened tone of voice and less energy, intense panic attacks during a public speaking experience, and physical signs such as trembling, sweating, clammy hands, hot/cold flushes, dry mouth, nausea, vomiting, dizziness or fainting, frequent urination, abdominal uneasiness and elevated heartbeat are all part of the experience of glossophobia (7). At a national level, testing conducted by the National Institute of Mental Health proved that the brains of people with social anxiety have a heightened response when negative comments were read to them. The affected areas were those responsible for self-evaluation and emotional processing. This heightened response wasn't seen in people without the disorder (8).

Rationale:

Glossophobia i.e. the fear of public speaking, is, in general, a major hindrance in educational success and an important prevailing factor in students of all kinds of professions. In our study, we decided to check the prevalence of glossophobia at one of the higher institutes of Pakistan (University of Lahore) to compare the incidence of this phobia between medical and non-medical students—students of the same institute, facing the same physical environment, irrespective of the difference of their professional environment. As a generally well known and accepted fact, that medical students have more stress of their studies and exceptional pressures, it has led them to the anxiety and the development of fear to speak or express their ideas in front of a public audience. The 'public' can be either the teacher conducting the viva, or their class fellows to whom they are giving presentations. So, we decided to find the percentage of students facing this general problem, as well as the factors and justifications behind this phobia, by comparing the level of this phobia among the medical and non-medical students. The purpose being to make amendments to overcome this problem in near future. International and national studies have already been conducted on this issue; however, not much research has been done in Pakistan. One of the major reasons in conducting this study was to get an idea of the prevalence of this phobia as well as to compare prevalence between medical and non medical students.

LITERATURE VIEW:

Anxiety is a physiological response defined as "a state of apprehension and uncertain fear" (9). Fear of public speaking—Glossophobia, can be more terrifying than death (Jerry Seinfeld). The degree of anxiety associated with Glossophobia can be so intense as to give rise to serious physical conditions such as suicidal ideations (10). Glossophobia tends to dominate over all social phobias and has been determined to be 46% of all social phobias (11). Gender has its influence in prevalence of public speaking anxiety and has shown that Glossophobia is more among young females because of the feeling of intimidation (12).

In the past two decades, there has been a myriad of research in language anxiety. According to a research, 74% of Americans suffer from speech anxiety (National Institute of Mental Health). According to a study in 1986, public speaking anxiety dominated many fears in Americans such as going to a dentist, earthquakes, floods, hurricanes, dying or theft.

- I feel anxious
- Realizing that only a little time remains makes me very tense and anxious.
- While giving a speech, I know I can control my feeling of stress and tension.
- I breathe faster just while waiting to give my speech.
- I have trouble falling asleep the night before a speech.
- When I make a mistake while giving a speech, I find it hard to concentrate on the parts that follow.
- I look forward to giving a speech.
- I feel comfortable and relaxed in the hour or so just before giving a speech.
- I do not dread giving a speech.
- I feel anxious when asked to answer a question in front of the class.
- I volunteer to speak on behalf of my group when needed.
- I avoid being called on in class out of fear of speaking.
- I can handle troublesome situations easily with my words.
- I can easily talk to a group of strangers without any feeling of embarrassment.
- When spontaneously asked to speak, my voice begins to shake.
- While walking on stage, I start to sweat and my hands tremble.
- I like initiating conversations in a public gathering.

RESULTS:

Medical Data

I have no fear of giving a speech

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Strongly Disagree	10	13.3	13.3	13.3
Disagree	31	41.3	41.3	54.7
Neutral	15	20.0	20.0	74.7
Agree	11	14.7	14.7	89.3
Strongly Agree	8	10.7	10.7	100.0
Total	75	100.0	100.0	

This frequency distribution table shows 41.3% of students disagreed to the question that they don't fear giving a speech while on the same grounds 14.7% of students agreed on the fact that they don't fear giving

speech. however, 13.3% of people strongly disagreed while 10.47% of people strongly agreed the same question.

Non-Medical Data

I have no fear of giving a speech

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Strongly Disagree	3	4.0	4.0	4.0
Disagree	21	28.0	28.0	32.0
Neutral	17	22.7	22.7	54.7
Agree	22	29.3	29.3	84.0
Strongly Agree	12	16.0	16.0	100.0
Total	75	100.0	100.0	

The same question was asked among non medical students' data showed us that 28% of non medical students disagreed with the question that do not fear giving a speech.while in the same circumstances 29% agreed to the same question.16% of students strongly agreed that they don't have fear of speech while only 4% strongly disagreed to the question.

Comparsion:

Non medical students are found more confident at bringing up a speech. This question was asked to determine the confidence level , medical students here were found to suffer from more social anxiety level as prevalence is high among medical student

Medical Data:

The question was asked among medical students if they feel tensed and nervous while preparing for the speech. The results we got is illustrated in this bar chart. This shows majority of medical students agreed on the fact that they get nervous and tensed. Students disagreeing on the question were in a small number while a good number of students strongly agreed with the question.

Non-Medical Data:

The same question was put among the non medical students in the same grades. The results were almost same. The majority answered in the favour of social anxiety. The students agreeing and strongly agreeing with the question, made the majority. The number of students who marked the neutral was higher than the students who disagreed with the question. However the prevalence of social anxiety was relatively high

Medical Data :

Comparison:

The prevalence of Glossophobia was found higher among medical students. 84% of medical students agreed to the question while on the other hand 66% of non medical students agreed to the same question.

This question was asked to check the relativity of tachycardia with social anxiety level. The results were favourable. 50.7% of students said that their heart beat really fast as they start the speech. Amazingly 25% strongly agreed to this fact. 8% of students disagreed while students strongly agreeing to the fact was not more than one percent. 14% of students marked the neutral option. This showed social anxiety is highly related to sympathetic activity.

Non-Medical Data :

On asking the same questions from non medical students, we found that 30% of students agreed on the question while 25% strongly agreed that their heart beat really fast when they start the speech. 12% percent of students disagreed and 5.3% of students strongly disagreed with this question. 25% of students marked neutral. This also favoured the fact of relativity of social anxiety with sympathetic activity.

Comparison:

76% of medical students proved the fact that their heart beat fast when they start the speech. 55% almost non medical students proved the same fact however prevalence was higher among medical students.

Medical Data:**I volunteer to speak on behalf of my group when needed**

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Strongly Disagree	5	6.7	6.7	6.7
Disagree	16	21.3	21.3	28.0
Neutral	25	33.3	33.3	61.3
Agree	23	30.7	30.7	92.0
Strongly Agree	6	8.0	8.0	100.0
Total	75	100.0	100.0	

A question was placed in front of medical students, whether take responsibility of speaking on the behalf their group to detect the prevalence of Glossophobia. 30% of students said that they do take this responsibility while 8% strongly agreed to that. 21.3% of students disagreed with the question asked. Whole 33% marked neutral.

Non-Medical Data :

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	8	10.7	10.7	10.7
	Disagree	11	14.7	14.7	25.3
	Neutral	22	29.3	29.3	54.7
	Agree	25	33.3	33.3	88.0
	Strongly Agree	9	12.0	12.0	100.0
	Total	75	100.0	100.0	

The same question was asked by non medical students and results showed us that 33% of students agreed with the answer and 14.7% disagreed that they would not speak on the behalf of their group if given option. 29% almost marked neutral.

Comparison:

45% of non medical students said that they would volunteer to represent on the behalf of their group. On the same question 38% of medical agreed to volunteer. Confidence level was found higher among non medical students.

Medical Data :

This question was asked from students if they suffer anxiety while waiting to give speech. 48% of students answered that they do suffer anxiety while waiting to give speech while 14% students disagreed to this fact. 24% students answered neutral while 8% students marked strongly agree to this question.

Non Medical Data:

The same question was asked from non medical students and 30% of them agreed that they do fear anxiety while waiting for a speech, 25 % of them marked neutral while 26.7% disagreed that they don't fear such an anxiety before delivering a public speech.

Comparison:

Comparably higher percentage of medical students agreed that they suffer anxiety while waiting to give speech while comparatively low number of non medical students agreed to that. Social anxiety level was found higher among medical students.

Medical Data :

On asking this question, 38% of students agreed that they can handle troublesome situations while speaking in public. 22% said that they cannot handle such situation due to confusion state. 25% of students marked neutral option.

Non-Medical Data:

When the same question was asked from non medical students we found out that 36% of people think that they can handle such troublesome situation while 16% of students think that they can not handle such situation if they come across. 22% strongly agreed to the situation while 21% of students were found marking neutral option.

COMPARISON:

38% of medical students think that they can handle troublesome situation if they come across during any public speech. While on the same question 58% of non medical agreed to the answer. This again conclude that prevalence was Glossophobia was high among medical students.

Prevalence of Glossophobia was calculated and it turned out to be 53% among medical students. Prevalence among non medical was 43.35%. The results clearly showed that prevalence of Glossophobia was higher among medical students of University of Lahore.

DISCUSSION:

Glossophobia i.e. public speaking anxiety is an important issue and hurdle to success in accord to not able to fully express the ideas in the life of the

students. To check the prevalence of this issue we did our study in the University of Lahore comparing its level in the medical and non -medical students regardless of the gender. In our study, we made questionnaire comprising of that type of questions which cover the area of only university environment and the study curriculum excluding their home environment that can also use in the future study. In our study, in response to question of having no fear in giving speech was extraordinary negative in medical students almost 41.3% disagreed to this question and only 14.7% students agreed that they have no fear in giving speech. The response of non-medical students to this was against to the medical ones. In non-medical students 28% disagreed while 29% agreed to this question reflecting almost same % in non-medical.

Similarly in another question of feeling tense and anxious in delivering speech, the response of agreed ones to this question was more in medical as compared to the non-medicals but the percentage of the agreed students in both were high than disagreed ones reflecting the high prevalence of social anxiety.

In another study of Manchester Metropolitan University, conducted by Hassan Waheed in July

2014, on the topic of Glossophobia among non-clinical students also reflect the high prevalence of social anxiety in the students. This study also compare the level in male and female. We excluded this factor in our study due to the lack of data.

The prevalence we calculated from our results for medical students was 53%. According to a research among Karachi medical colleges the prevalence was 41.3 exhibit low anxiety level 54.8 exhibit moderate level of anxiety and 3.8 were found to suffer high level anxiety. Our objective was to compare the prevalence among medical and non medical students of University of Lahore. The prevalence among non medical was 43.35 percent. The prevalence of social anxiety level for medical students was high than non medical students of the same grade and same institute.

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